

Results and Discussions

The pesticidal properties of compounds were evaluated by method described earlier¹. The results are tabulated in Table 1.

Their fungicidal properties were best exhibited in compounds based on caprylic, lauric and myristic acids (8, 12 and 14 carbon atoms) in respect of *Chetomium globosum* and *Rhizoctonia solani* but *Aspergillus niger* was mainly inhibited by the caprate compounds. This is in consonance with the observation of Seigler and Popenoe⁴ as well as Diels and Menusan⁸, both of whom have observed maximum fungicidal and insecticidal properties in fatty acids of 10 and 12 carbon atoms found in capric and lauric acids.

In alcohol series, compounds developed on lauryl, heptyl and cetyl groups with 12, 7 and 16 carbon atom chains show greater fungitoxicity as compared to others. Individually they are most effective against *Chetomium globosum* and *Rhizoctonia solani* and *A.n.* is inhibited by compounds of lauryl alcohol. This behaviour closely supports the observation of Kears and Sijpesteijn⁹ and Zedler and Bieter¹⁰ who observed maximum activity of alkyl tin acetate associated with 9 and 12 carbon atoms.

In respect of bactericidal properties of aliphatic acids and alcohols it was observed that practically the same acid derived compounds which exhibited fungitoxic properties also show strong bactericidal character. In this respect maximum potentialities were exhibited by compounds containing 8, 10 and 12 carbon atoms. In compounds of aliphatic alcohols the bactericidal properties were mainly concentrated around those derived from 7, 12 and 16 carbon atoms.

Individually the compounds showed strong bactericidal action against *Escherichia coli* in descending order in case of caprate, carpylate, and laurate while in *Staphylococcus aureus* it was in order of laurate, caprate and caprylate. The compounds from alcohols developed on lauryl, heptyl and butyl group show better response on *Escherichia coli* and those developed on cetyl, heptyl and lauryl groups against *Staphylococcus aureus*. Strong bactericidal characters of alkyl tin compounds have also been reported by Zedler and Bieter as well as Sijpesteijn *et al.*, together with that observed by Vanderkerk and Luijten. It could be concluded that the new tin compounds based on both aliphatic acids and alcohols have a very strong potential for crop protection work.

Acknowledgement

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Flavones, Flavonols and Flavanones Derived from 2'-Hydroxy-4'-*n*-Butoxy Chalkones

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BY selenium dioxide oxidation and the alkaline hydrogen peroxide oxidation, 2'-hydroxy-4'-*n*-butoxychalkone gives flavone and flavonol respectively. 2'-Hydroxychalkone on cyclisation with dilute sulphuric acid or hydrochloric acid gives flavanones.

In this paper the synthesis of flavones, flavonols and flavanones from 2'-hydroxy-4'-*n*-butoxychalkones¹ is described when 2'-hydroxy-4'-*n*-butoxychalkone were subjected to selenium dioxide oxidation in dry *n*-amyl alcohol, 7-*n*-butoxyflavones were obtained. The chalkone dibromides¹ were refluxed with anhydrous potassium carbonate in acetone to give flavones.

The chalkones were subjected to the Algar-Flynn oxidation using alkaline hydrogen peroxide when 7-*n*-butoxy flavonols were obtained. The acetyl derivatives of flavonols were prepared using flavonol, acetic anhydride and pyridine. 2'-Hydroxy-4'-*n*-butoxychalkones were cyclised to 7-*n*-butoxyflavanones using dilute sulphuric acid.

Experimental

General procedure. (a) A mixture of the 2'-hydroxy-4'-*n*-butoxychalkone (1.0 g) and dry selenium dioxide (1.0 g) in dry *n*-amyl alcohol (15 ml) was refluxed in an oil-bath at 130°–140° for 24 hrs. The precipitated selenium was filtered off and the filtrate steam distilled to remove the alcohol. The product remained in the flask was collected and crystallised from methanol. It is insoluble in alkali and it does not give colour with alcoholic ferric chloride. The flavones prepared are recorded in Table 1.

(b) A mixture of 2'-Hydroxy-4'-*n*-butoxy- α - β -dibromochalkone (0.5 g) and potassium carbonate (0.5 g) in acetone (25 ml) was refluxed on a water bath at 70° for 4 hr. The solution was filtered when

TABLE 1—7-*n*-BUTOXYFLAVONES

No.	Substituent R	Crystal form	M.P. °C	Formula	%Found		%Calcd.	
1.	H	Pale brown	112	C ₁₉ H ₁₈ O	C, H,	77.4 6.2	C, H,	77.56 6.12
2.	4'-Methoxy	Pale brown	115	C ₂₀ H ₂₀ O ₄	C, H,	73.9 6.1	C, H,	74.08 6.17
3.	3'-4'-Methylenedioxy	Pinkish white	178	C ₂₀ H ₁₈ O ₅	C, H,	70.9 5.2	C, H,	71.01 5.32
4.	3'-4'-Dimethoxy	Yellow	108	C ₂₁ H ₂₂ O ₅	C, H,	71.0 6.1	C, H,	71.19 6.21
5.	3'-Methoxy-4'-ethoxy	Pale yellow	141	C ₂₂ H ₂₄ O ₅	C, H,	71.6 6.4	C, H,	71.74 6.52
6.	4'-Chloro	Pale brown	147	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ O ₃ Cl	Cl,	10.7	Cl	10.08

TABLE 2—7-*n*-BUTOXYFLAVONOLS

No.	Substituent R	Crystal form	M.P. °C	Formula	%Found		%Calcd.	
1.	H	Colourless	139	C ₁₉ H ₁₈ O ₄	C, H,	73.4 5.7	C, H,	73.53 5.80
	Acetyl derivative of (1)	Pale yellow	91	C ₂₁ H ₂₀ O ₅	C, H,	71.4 5.5	C, H,	71.60 5.68
2.	4'-Methoxy	Yellow	143	C ₂₀ H ₂₀ O ₆	C, H,	70.4 6.0	C, H,	70.58 5.88
	Acetyl derivative of (2)	Pale yellow	126	C ₂₂ H ₂₂ O ₆	C, H,	69.0 5.6	C, H,	69.10 5.76
3.	3'-4'-Methylenedioxy	Yellow	168	C ₂₀ H ₁₈ O ₆	C, H,	67.6 4.9	C, H,	67.79 5.06
	Acetyl derivative of (3)	Colourless	181	C ₂₂ H ₂₀ O ₇	C, H,	66.5 4.9	C, H,	66.67 5.05
4.	3'-4'-Dimethoxy	Pale yellow	150	C ₂₁ H ₂₂ O ₆	C, H,	68.03 5.8	C, H,	68.11 5.94
	Acetyl derivative of (4)	Pale yellow	131	C ₂₃ H ₂₄ O ₇	C, H,	66.9 5.7	C, H,	67.00 5.82
5.	3'-Methoxy-4'-ethoxy	Pale yellow	140	C ₂₂ H ₂₄ O ₆	C, H,	68.6 6.1	C, H,	68.76 6.25
	Acetyl derivative of (5)	Pale yellow	134	C ₂₄ H ₂₆ O ₇	C, H,	67.5 6.0	C, H,	67.61 6.10
6.	4'-Chloro	Colourless	141	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ O ₄ Cl	Cl,	10.6	Cl,	10.53
	Acetyl derivative of (6)	Colourless	231	C ₃₁ H ₁₉ O ₅ Cl	Cl,	9.1	Cl,	9.17

TABLE 3—7-*n*-BUTOXYFLAVANONES

No.	Substituent R	M.P. °C	Formula	%Found		%Calcd.	
1.	H	72	C ₁₉ H ₂₀ O ₃	C, H,	77.1 6.87	C, H,	77.02 6.75
2.	4'-Methoxy	82	C ₂₀ H ₂₂ O ₄	C, H,	73.5 6.6	C, H,	73.62 6.75
3.	3'-4'-Methylenedioxy	98	C ₂₀ H ₂₀ O ₅	C, H,	70.4 5.8	C, H,	70.58 5.88
4.	3'-4'-Dimethoxy	98	C ₂₁ H ₂₄ O ₅	C, H,	70.9 6.8	C, H,	70.79 6.74
5.	3'-Methoxy-4'-ethoxy	125	C ₂₂ H ₂₆ O ₅	C, H,	71.2 6.9	C, H,	71.36 7.03
6.	4'-Chloro	101	C ₁₉ H ₁₉ O ₃ Cl	Cl,	10.6	Cl,	10.74

hot and acetone was removed, when a pale brown product was obtained. It was crystallised from ethanol. The mixed m.p. with 7-*n*-butoxy flavone obtained by oxidation of the chalcone by selenium dioxide was not lowered.

7-*n*-Butoxy flavonol: The chalcone (0.5 g) was mixed with NaOH (15 ml, 10%) and then methanol (15 ml) was added. The mixture was warmed, if necessary to obtain a clear solution. It was cooled in ice, H₂O₂ (4 ml., 17%) was added and left in ice-bath for 2 hr and then overnight at room temperature. It turned greenish yellow. It was then poured into ice-water and acidified. The substance was collected and crystallised from ethanol. It develops a greenish fluorescence with conc. H₂SO₄. The flavonols thus obtained are recorded in Table 2.

7-*n*-Butoxy flavanones: 2'-Hydroxy-4'-*n*-butoxy-chalcone (0.5 g) in ethanol (30 ml) was treated with sulphuric acid (20 ml; 10%) when turbidity appeared. It was dissolved by adding more ethanol (10 ml) and the solution was refluxed on a water-bath for 24 hr. Ethanol was then distilled off and the residual solution was filtered hot and left at room temperature when flavanone was obtained. It was crystallised from petrol-ether colourless crystals. The results are summarised in Table 3.

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Spectrophotometric and Conductometric study of Chelates of Divalent Calcium and Divalent Zinc with 2-hydroxy-1,4-naphthoquinone (Lawsonie)

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SURVEY of literature reveals that 2-hydroxy-1,4-naphthoquinone (Lawsonie) has found its application in qualitative and quantitative estimations of various metals¹⁻⁴. Recently we have reported the chelate of Lawsonie with lanthanum⁵ spectrophotometrically and conductometrically.

Experimental

Standard solutions of Lawsonie (K.K. Laboratories I.N.C. Plainview, New York, A.R.) and Calcium

nitrate and Zinc nitrate of B.D.H. AnalaR grade were prepared by dissolving the respective compound in double distilled ethyl alcohol (absolute).

To isolate the complexes, 200 ml of Lawsonie (alcoholic) solution (0.01M) was added slowly to the beaker containing 200 ml of metal ions (0.01M) with constant stirring. After addition the solution was warmed and allowed to stand overnight. The yellowishred (Ca-lawsonie complex) and pomegranate red (Zn-Lawsonie complex) coloured crystals appeared, were filtered, and washed several times with ice-cold water and dried at 70°-75° and 62°-68° respectively.

The isolated complexes were analysed for metal content gravimetrically.

Baush and Lomb spectronic-20 spectrophotometer for absorbance measurements, Perkin-Elmer infrared spectrophotometer for infra-red spectra, were used.

Results and Discussion

It has been observed that the order of addition of reactants had no appreciable effect on absorbance.

Nature of chelates

To find the nature of chelates formed and working wave length Garg, Singh and Kotyal⁶ method was used. For this, mixtures containing equal proportions of metal ions and lawsonie were mixed and the absorbance measured. The absorption maximum of the complex were found to be at 475 nm and 465 nm respectively.

Composition of the chelates

The composition of the chelates were established by the method of Job's continuous variation⁷, molar ratio⁸, slope ratio⁹ and Dey¹⁰. A large number of observations were taken at 475 nm and 465 nm and it was found that the ratio of Ca⁺⁺ Lawsonie and Zn⁺⁺ : Lawsonie is 1 : 1 in each case.

Molecular Formula of the Chelate

Chemical analysis of Ca-Lawsonie chelate

From analysis it was found that amount of calcium, C and H are 10.7%, 45.6% and 4.7% and calculated values are 10.9%, 45.7% and 4.6% respectively which correspond to the formula [(C₁₀H₅O₃)(Ca)(C₂H₅OH)₂]⁺NO₃⁻.

The fact that nitrate is not in coordination sphere was further confirmed by conductance shown by chelate in alcoholic solution.

Chemical analysis of Zn-Lawsonie chelate

In Zn-Lawsonie chelate the % of Zn, C and H are 16.2%, 42.6% and 4.4% and the calculated values are 16.5%, 42.8% and 4.3% respectively which correspond to the formula

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